

MULTIAXIAL FAILURE CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this research has been to develop a multiaxial testing capability for continuous fiber composites using the axial/torsion/internal pressurization of tubes. This capability enables one to generate the two-dimensional (in-plane) failure surface for these materials. The multiaxial test specimen consists of a 5.08 cm (2.0") diameter composite tube with 15° cast epoxy end cones for gripping. The unique advancement with this new technique is the simple, but very efficient, gripping mechanism that provides a very smooth transition in load from the grip into the specimen. This has eliminated grip related stress risers in the composite tube. Consequently, most of the failures occur in the gage section of the tube. This system is coupled into a biaxial MTS servo hydraulic test machine capable of simultaneously applying axial load, torque, and internal pressure, providing one complete control of the axial, transverse, and shear stresses that develop in the wall of the composite tube. This paper will present the failure results obtained to date for various laminate configurations of Toray 1000/DER332-T403 filament wound carbon/epoxy tubes along with T300/F263 prepreg carbon/epoxy tubes. The goal of our efforts is to develop a more fully characterized three-dimensional failure criterion for these materials. This model will then be incorporated into a large three-dimensional orthotropic finite element model for structural analysis as well as a specialized three-dimensional orthotropic finite element model capable of detailed sub-ply level analysis on sub-structural components.

Key Words: Composites, Multiaxial, Failure, Testing/Evaluation

1. INTRODUCTION

At the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) we have been developing fibrous composite structures for use in challenging three-dimensional loading environments such as penetrator cases and advanced munition components. A major difficulty in designing these structures is the ability to characterize and model the three-dimensional performance (constitutive and failure behavior) of these materials. The load requirements for some LLNL structural designs require working loads close to the actual catastrophic failure loads and in some cases we may even tolerate a limited amount of structural failure. The optimization of these designs requires a greater understanding of the full three-dimensional failure behavior for these materials. Generic hands off three-dimensional failure models simply don't exist at the present time and the validity of using current failure criterion (max stress, max strain, Tsai-Wu [1], Feng [2], Christensen [3], etc.) has not been well established for three-dimensionally loaded composite structures. To add further complications it is difficult to accurately model the three-dimensional elastic constitutive response for these materials. Thus we are limited in our ability to track the local stress strain fields necessary for failure evaluation.

A key factor in characterizing any failure criterion rests with the ability to determine the necessary experimental failure strengths. A myriad of complex failure modes are possible for continuous fiber composite materials, with different failure modes possible for different laminate configurations. These modes can even be path dependent. To adequately describe this behavior it is necessary to generate failure surfaces. Whether one can use the failure surface from a single ply to predict the complex failure surfaces possible for multiply oriented thick composites must be resolved. This question is governed by how many multiaxial data points are required to adequately characterize a given failure criterion for use in three-dimensional design. This is a fully cost driven constraint. To minimize this cost we need to better understand how the composite performance varies when we select a different fiber, matrix, and laminate orientation. Another real cost limiting factor for large scale applications is how does poor fabrication quality affect performance. Only through controlled multiaxial testing can we begin to answer these fundamental questions.

In order to better characterize and evaluate the three-dimensional performance of these materials we have developed a multiaxial testing capability. Determination of the actual complex multiaxial failure surfaces will enhance the ability to characterize and develop failure criteria. But more importantly, to properly evaluate a failure criterion one must have the multiaxial loading environments.

Forms of multiaxial testing include axial/torsion/internal pressurization of tubes [4,5], in-plane biaxial loading of plates [4,6], out-of-plane loading of simply supported plates [7,8], three-dimensional compression [9], internal pressurization of thin-walled pressure vessels, and axial

compression of external compression rings. There have been attempts by some to perform external pressurization of the axial/torsion tubes to induce further stresses, however this can be a complicated and expensive setup [10]. Fully controlled three-dimensional loading of composite structures will probably never exist, however one can superimpose various forms of the available multiaxial tests to construct some of the three-dimensional failure surfaces.

The axial / torsion / internal pressurization of thin walled composite tubes is considered the most complete form of biaxial or multiaxial testing available. It best fulfills the requirements of having a primarily homogeneous stress state in the gage section and that the state of stress is known without any secondary measurement or analysis [4]. The limited application of this technique has been due to the difficulties associated with introducing loads into the specimen and still maintaining failure initiation in the gage section. The expense of fabricating uniform quality specimens has also limited application.

2. DISCUSSION OF THE MULTIAXIAL TEST SYSTEM

2.1 Overcoming Load Introduction Problems

The objective of the gripping mechanism design was to uniformly grip the composite without introducing any stress risers or out-of-plane displacements. To always insure proper contact between the composite and the grip, the idea of using stacked concentric cones was developed. That is, three hollow concentric cones can always be stacked on top of each other with total contact. The middle cone would represent the test specimen, the inside cone is used to prevent the middle cone from collapsing, and by pulling the outer cone over the middle cone load is thereby introduced into the specimen. The cones also behave like wedges. The more you tighten the outer cone the higher the gripping force. This force is always uniformly balanced by the presence of the inner cone. A 15° angle was chosen to give a reasonable amount of wedge action to the grips but mainly it looked esthetically correct.

Our first test specimen design consisted of 5.0 cm (2.0") composite tubes with integrally flared 15° ends. A diagram of the complete grip setup is shown in Fig. 1. A photograph of the test specimen is included. Load introduction into the composite test specimen is accomplished as follows: the flared composite test specimen is placed over the inner 15° cone; a pair of precision machined 15° split wedges are then inserted over the flared ends of the test specimen; the load transfer collar is then used to apply compressive load to the split wedges which in turn reacts against the flared face of the test specimen. Originally we used a large single torquing nut that threaded into the load transfer collar to induce compression of the split wedges. But, this proved ineffective in that extremely large torques were required on the nut to gain any substantial axial loading across the cones. This setup was changed to the present method of using 12 (3/4 x 10) hardened cap screws to induce the compression of the split wedges.

The grip is connected to an MTS axial torsion machine rated to 222 KN axial force and 2260 N-m torsion (50,000 lbs axial and 20,000 in-lbs. torsion).

Pressurization of the test specimen was performed using a 345 MPa (50,000 psi) MTS pump system that was down graded to a working pressure of 69 MPa (10,000 psi) in order to accommodate the working loads possible for the multiaxial grips. Pressurization of the flared composite tube was not without difficulty. A thin bladder was necessary to insure a macroscopic failure. Without the bladder multiple tiny leaks usually occurred without any real structural degradation in axial load bearing capability of the tube.

Figure 1. Diagram of multiaxial test system for 5.08 cm diameter composite tubes with the integrally flared 15° end cones for gripping.

2.2 Fabrication of Test Specimen

These first tubes were all fabricated from pre-preg graphite/epoxy tape with gage lengths in either 15.24 cm (6.0") or 5.08 cm (2.0"). The 5.08 cm tube was preferred. The pre-preg was hand laid over a split aluminum mandrel incorporating the 15° flared ends. A 5 cm radius was machined into the mandrel in the transition region. 0/90 fabric was incorporated in the flared region to provide more material for uniform gripping. This was necessary to fill the voids in material created when laying the pre-preg tape up the side of the 15° flared mandrel. The fabric was extended about 1.25 cm into the gage section of the composite tube. This technique provided a sufficient amount of gripping force to the actual composite tube material. Silicon clam shells

were incorporated on the outside of the mandrel to prevent wrinkling of the test section from vacuum bagging during autoclave curing. This type of specimen proved to be very difficult and time consuming to fabricate with the required necessary quality. Nevertheless we were able to fabricate enough specimens to evaluate the potential of the multiaxial test system. This configuration was first used to evaluate the multiaxial behavior of T300/F263 pre-preg carbon/epoxy tubes until major limitations of the system were encountered.

2.3 Limitations of the First Design

The biggest limitation of the first design was that it would not accommodate evaluation of filament wound materials. We could not wind the necessary low angle fiber orientations using the flared composite tube mandrel, the minimum angle was $\pm 30^\circ$. To facilitate low angle filament winding only a straight tube would suffice. And with the straight tube we could no longer utilize the full benefits of the concentric cone approach. The second difficulty with the integrally flared end cone was achieving a good seal on the pressure bladder. Finally, quality fabrication of the integrally flared composite tubes was expensive and time consuming.

2.4 Redesign of Multiaxial Test System

Overall the external geometry of the test specimen was maintained including the 15° gripping flare on each end of the composite tube. The first change was replacing the 15° inner compression cone with a removable straight compression plug. Again, the purpose of the inner compression plug is to resist the radial deformation of the composite test specimen during gripping from the external 15° split wedges. Multiple sets of the internal compression plugs have been machined with very small changes in the outside diameter to accommodate small variations in the internal diameter of the test specimen resulting from changes in laminate configuration. To minimize the transverse and radial displacement constraints of the composite test specimen in the transition region from the flare to straight tube, both the 15° split wedges and the internal compression plug have a machined radius of curvature. This further minimized the local stress risers in the tube which could cause premature failure in the test specimen.

The major change was in developing the external 15° flared end cone. Such ideas as building up the 15° flare with continuous fiber wraps and bonding solid reusable aluminum cones were investigated. The problem with both of these approaches is that they severely constrain the transverse and radial displacements of the tube in the transition region. The solution to this problem was to cast the 15° flares out of epoxy and it has worked ever since. The cast epoxy cone is fairly compliant when compared to the stiffness of the composite tube.

A diagram of the redesigned multiaxial gripping system is shown in Fig. 2 and a diagram of the multiaxial test specimen defining load orientation and coordinate system used is shown in Fig. 3. A series of photographs depicting this system are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 2. Diagram of the multi-axial test system for 5.08 cm diameter composite tubes with the 15° cast epoxy end gripping cones.

2.5 Fabrication of the 15° Epoxy Gripping Cone

The 15° flared epoxy cones are cast directly onto the end of the composite tube. A split 15° aluminum mandrel is inserted over the composite tube. To insure concentric alignment 2 o-ring grooves have been machined into the inner shoulder of the split aluminum mandrel. As the split mandrel is bolted together the 2 o-rings force the composite tube to the center of the mandrel. Different sized o-rings are necessary to accommodate different tube diameters. The top o-ring also serves has a seal to prevent the wet epoxy from leaking down the tube during cure. The epoxy used for casting is DER332-T403. These unreinforced cast epoxy cones are capable of transferring over 489 kN of axial load before failure. Beyond this failure of the epoxy begins with large scale plastic deformation in the form of extrusion of the epoxy out of the gripping mechanism. A stiffer reinforced epoxy cone could transfer much higher axial loads. It may also be necessary at times to minimize the epoxy cone from shrinking during cure. This can be accomplished by the addition of a filler or one can add additional hoop reinforcement in the cone region before casting to minimize the cure shrinking on very thin-walled tubes.

Figure 3. Load description and fiber orientations for the multiaxial test specimen.

3. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

3.1 Integrally Flared Tube

The first multiaxial failure surface was generated using a T300/F263 pre-preg tape specimen with a $[0, 45, -45, 86, -86, -45, 45, 0]_T$ laminate orientation. This data was generated using the original 15° integrally flared tube design. The $\pm 86^\circ$ sequence resulted from using 0.6 cm wide tape for winding the pseudo 90° orientations. The multiaxial failure surface for this laminated composite is shown in Fig. 5. A series of photographs depicting tube failures is shown in Fig. 6. The stress values are based on thin-walled tube analysis. Each data point shown represents only a single test. The repeatability and accuracy of this data is unknown. However, one method used to judge the individual accuracy of a failure data point is whether it lies outside the line of minimum convexity for the overall failure surface. This imaginary line is drawn between successive data points in the failure surface. It is believed that a composite failure surface must always obey the convexity constraints.

The path dependency of the composite failure data is shown in this data. The shear strength at 50% tension is higher than the corresponding shear strength at 0% tension. Thus by initially applying tension to the quasi-isotropic tube one can obtain an increase in the available shear strength. The reverse is not true and we have a load path dependent failure. This unusual result can be explained using the "maximum strain" failure criterion. Under pure torsion failure is initiated in the laminate as a result of a compression failure in one of the 45° plies. The 45° ply will fail in compression before the opposing 45° plies (which are in tension) because of the large difference in the unidirectional tensile and compressive failure strains. By applying pre-tension

Figure 4. Photographic depiction of the multi-axial test system.

to the composite tube the effective compressive strains in the 45° plies are decreased and thus increasing the amount of torsional shear stress required to induce failure. Overall the integrally flared tube design performed very well but due to the previously mentioned limitations we changed to the straight composite tube design.

Figure 5. Multiaxial failure surface for a T300/F263 $[0, 45, -45, 86, -86, -45, 45, 0]$ laminate using the multiaxial testing system with the 15° integrally flared 5.08 cm composite tubes.

3.2 Straight Composite Tube with Cast 15° Epoxy Gripping Cones

The next multiaxial failure surfaces were generated using a filament wound Toray 1000/DER332-T403 carbon/epoxy specimen with a $[\pm 1.5, \pm 45, \pm 89]_T$ laminate orientation. This data was generated using the redesigned test specimen consisting of the 5.08 cm straight composite tube and the 15° cast epoxy gripping cones. The multiaxial failure surfaces for this material system is shown in Fig. 7 and a series of photographs depicting actual failures are shown in Fig. 8. This material system is over 2.5 times the tensile strength than the previous T300/F263 material system. The unidirectional strength of a filament wound Toray 1000/DER332-T403 system is over 3790 MPa as compared to 1481 MPa for the T300/F263 unidirectional configuration. The failure data shown for the axial/hoop stress curve (Fig. 7a) appears to be very well behaved. Except for a few stray data points the results seem to follow our minimum convexity conditions. These results follow the same trends reported by Swanson [5].

The hoop stresses were obtained by internally pressurizing the composite tubes. In order to insure a macroscopic hoop failure it was necessary to utilize an internal pressure bladder. The best results were obtained by constructing the bladder from a 0.2 mm thick sheet of plasticized pvc and seaming it with an appropriate adhesive.

Tension

Compression

Torsion

Internal Pressure

Tension/Torsion

Tension/Torsion

Figure 6. Failure examples for T300/F263 $[0, \pm 45, \pm 86, \pm 86, \pm 45, 0]_T$ graphite/epoxy laminated composite tubes.

a) axial/hoop stress failure data

b) axial/shear stress failure data

Figure 7. Multiaxial failure surface for a filament wound Toray 1000/DER332-T403 $[\pm 1.5, \pm 45, \pm 89]$ carbon/epoxy laminate using the 5.08 cm composite straight tube and the 15° cast epoxy gripping cones.

Tension

Compression

Compression

Torsion

Internal Pressure

Tension/Internal Pressure

Figure 8. Failure examples for filament wound Toray 1000/DER332-T403 $[\pm 1.5, \pm 45, \pm 89]_T$ composite tubes.

The axial/shear stress curve (Fig. 7b) has a lot more scatter in the data than did the axial/hoop stress curve. The outer boundary of this curve still appears to follow the minimum convexity conditions. The scatter can be attributed to several factors. First of all scatter has always been more prevalent when conducting shear testing. Fabrication flaws from the filament winding of the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers could be attributing to the scatter, especially since torsional failure initiates as a result of compression failure in the 45° plies. Furthermore the torsional response of an inter-woven $\pm 45^\circ$ filament wound layer is more complex than a corresponding $\pm 45^\circ$ pre-preg system. A future study of the axial/torsional behavior of a $\pm 45^\circ$ filament wound tube will provide some additional understanding of this problem.

The axial/hoop/shear data is shown in Fig. 7a. Only 2 data points have been generated to date. An interesting point about this data is that it shows an increase in the available shear strength for the composite tube with an application of the internal pressurization in addition to the axial tension. The additional internal pressurization could be providing constraint against possible torsional buckling. The combination of axial tension and internal pressure results in a small amount of hydrostatic pressure acting on the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers which could account for the increase in the available shear strength. An internal pressure of 4800 psi was required to generate a hoop stress of 689 MPa.

3.3 Compression Response of Helically Wrapped Composite Tubes

A compression study was performed on a series of filament wound $[\pm\theta, \pm\theta, 89]_T$ Toray 1000/DER332-T403 composite tubes. The $\pm\theta$ fiber orientation included $\pm 1.5^\circ$, $\pm 5^\circ$, $\pm 10^\circ$, $\pm 20^\circ$, and $\pm 45^\circ$. The single 89° layer was included to provide compaction of the helical layers. Because the multiaxial gripping system has eliminated the end effects we can easily characterize the compression performance of laminated composite materials. The results of this study are shown in Fig. 9. The results shown are preliminary since only 2 test were conducted for each laminate shown. Nevertheless, the only laminate that showed any deviation in the results was the $\pm 10^\circ$ configuration. The result shown represents the peak value obtained. The second test for this laminate had a compressive strength of 592 MPa. The lower compression strengths for the $\pm 1.5^\circ$ and $\pm 5.0^\circ$ laminates are attributed to the problems stemming from fabrication. It is very difficult to achieve the same compaction of fibers that is possible with the higher helical orientations. As the fiber angle decreases the effective fiber volume fraction decreases also. The coarse interwoven nature of the filament wound $\pm 1.5^\circ$ and $\pm 5.0^\circ$ laminates promotes an increase in fiber waviness and voids. Both of which are detrimental to the compression strength of the composite laminate. All of the failures in this study occurred in the center of the gage section.

Figure 9. Axial compression of $[\pm\theta, \pm\theta, 89]_T$ Toray 1000/DER332-T403 5.08 cm composite tubes

4.0 SUMMARY

A technique which allows testing of 5.08 cm diameter composite tubes under a combination of tension, compression, torsion, and internal pressurization has been developed. The unique advancement with this technique is the simple but very efficient gripping mechanism. The tapered 15° cone provides an extremely smooth transition in load between the grip and the composite test specimen. Furthermore, the 15° epoxy cone induces minimal constraints on the transverse and radial displacement of the composite tube outside of the split wedge containment. This combined effect has eliminated the grip induced failures, providing one with a high degree of confidence in the resulting material failures. The cast epoxy cones have also eliminated some of the complexity and cost associated with multiaxial testing. The unreinforced cast epoxy cones are capable of transferring up to 489 KN (110,000 lbs.) of axial force to a test specimen. This gives one a substantial capability for inducing failure in virtually any type of 5.08 cm diameter tube. The high load transferring capability is due to the near hydrostatic compression that develops between the bond line of the 15° epoxy cone and the composite tube from the gripping apparatus. Hydrostatic compression has been shown to significantly increase the available shear strength of an epoxy joint [11,12].

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